
AGRICULTURE STATUS OF SHIRGOAN VILLAGE IN MAVAL TAHSIL OF PUNE DISTRICT IN MAHARASHTRA, INDIA

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Abstract:

Shirgoan village as part of the rural settlement which can always effect the rural environment of nearby location. Socio-economic status of shirgoan village is mostly depended on education, income and occupation. Socio-economic condition makes much effect on housing condition, living condition, life style, education, health and other all functions in rural area. The education and income are important elements for Socio-economic assessments of rural population.

The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data including the field survey with help of questioners and also collects the secondary data from grampanchayat of shirgoan village. This paper represent the Socio-economic assessments of shirgoan village with help of following parameters like, labour Force Participation, Agricultural Labour, Educational status, Language, & Caste status.

Key Words: - Field Survey, graphs, Tables and Various statistical techniques.

1. Introduction:

Shirgoan village is small village in Maval tahshil. The village shirgoan is developed with cultural as well as social factors. Geographical role is to understand this stage of cultural development and its relationship with natural environment.

The survey provides the primary data regarding different aspects of life style of man in the village. Environment has direct impact on village culture. Natural phenomenon directly governs the village setup. Therefore it is very important to study natural phenomenon along with human beings. The government of India and government of Maharashtra continuously try to develop the villages, as the 3/4th of the Indian population lives in this habitat. Government introduces many schemes for people's welfare. Urban people have least contact with villagers therefore it is necessary to visit the village to see the percolation extent of government plans and schemes to find out the problem and finally to conclude the suggestion.

2. Objective:

- To study the Agriculture status of Shirgaon village.
- To understand the social aspects of study area.

3. Methodology:

The primary data and secondary data have been used for the research paper. The questionnaire has been prepared to collect the data. The statistical method has been used for data calculation.

3.1: Data collection:

Data collection has done with the help of the observation, interviews, photos, Google images and field survey. Questionnaires have prepared for obtaining information of solid waste & tin-bin system. However spatial analysis of study area has been done on Google image using Arc GIS in to calculate area and related features.

4. Agriculture status

4.1: Land use pattern

The agriculture activity in the shirgaon is totally on monsoon dependent. Irrigation facility is not available in the village due to poverty of families. The total geographical area of village is 180.55 acre. This area has been utilized by following ways.

In the study area total land acre 180.55 acre. Divided many land use types. Agriculture land use 16.91% as well as under the forest is 6.38% therefore more than largest area covered by agriculture land use and minimum area covered by non agricultural land and is 0.98%. And 35.20% are un- irrigated land.

Table no 1. **Land use pattern**

Type Of Land Use	Area In (Acres)	Area In (%)
Forest	31	6.38%
Irrigated by source	20	4.11%
Un-irrigated	171.11	35.20%
Cultivable	78.64	16.19%
Area not available for cultivation	4.74	0.98%
Settlement	180.55	37.14%
Total	486.04	100.00%

Source: Own Sample Surveyed

4.2: Classification of soil in study Area:

4.2.1 Coarse black soil:

This type soil is basically found on the top of hill towards the hill slope. The thickness of soil is 2 to 3 cm. The coarse shallow soil has occupied 60 percent area. Due to its thickness the soil is not suitable for agriculture. Hills tops and hill slopes are occupied by open scrubs and thorny bushes.

4.2.2 Medium black soil:

Medium black soil is situated in foot hills zones in the central part. The soil formed due to the positional work by non-perennial streams. The thickness of the soil is 2 to 5 feet .The soil occupied almost 15 percent area. This soil is suitable for unirrigated crops like fodder, cereals and paddy.

4.2.3 Deep black soil:

The soil occupies 25 percent geographical area of the study region. The thickness of the soil is between 5 to 25 feet. This soil supports the crop like wheat, bajara, sugarcane, paddy etc.

Table no.2: **classification of soil**

Soil Types	Area In Acres	Area In %
Coarse black soil	300.75	61.87
Medium black soil	46.32	9.53
Deep black soil	138.97	28.59
Total	486.04	100

Source: Own Sample Surveyed

4.3: Gender wise population.

The total population of the village Shirgaon is 2187. The total number of households are 230 and the average family size is 4.99. Out of total population 51.66 percent is male population and 49.69 percent is female population. Sex ratio of village is 937.

Table no 3: Gender wise population.

Gender	No Of Population	Population In %
Male	1129	51.63
female	1058	48.37
total	2187	100

Source: Own Sample Surveyed

4.4: Occupational status

From the blow table it can be shown that in rural main occupation of people is farming. They either work in their own land or for somebody else. There are 420 farmers in 2014 out of which 230 (20.37 %) are male & 190 (17.96%) are female farmers. We find in village shirgaon most of the people do not have enough land which they can still on their own to earn and living so they are mostly dependent on the other works that available to them. According to survey there are 329 (29.15%) Male and 290 (27.42%) female are found as a marginal workers out of total population in village. Agricultural Labour males are more which contribute 58.62. As per the no worker male population 8.86 percent where as female has 13.04 percent. The percentage of other workers is also considerable; male has 26.57 percent which as female has 26.46 percent.

Table no.4. Occupational status

Sr. No	Category	Male Population	Male Population In%	Female Population	Female Population In%
1	farmers	230	20.37	190	17.96
2	Agricultural Labors	170	15.05	160	15.12

3	Other Workers	300	26.57	280	26.46
4	Marginal Workers	329	29.15	290	27.42
5	No Workers	100	8.86	138	13.04
	Total	1129	100	1058	100

Source: Own Sample Surveyed

4.5: Educational status of study area

Education is necessary for the development of every sphere of human activity. It is the most important tools for income of household, health, hygiene and standard of living. The Village has an Anganwadi, a primary school name as Zillah Perished Primary School serves the Purpose of primary education.

Blow table shows the 0 to 04 std. Population is more in shirgaon. Because at the government are providing facilities for school going children such as free books, school uniform, educational stationary. They are giving fully attention on children's. Next higher population including class for 05 to 10 std. population is less. It indicates that the area of shirgaon is less educated.

Table no 5. Education status

level of educational	no of population	population in %
class 0 to 04	1002	45.82
Class 05 to 10	474	21.67
Class 11 to 12	299	13.67
Class 13 to 15	130	5.95
other	282	12.89
total	2187	100

Source: Own Sample Surveyed

6. Conclusion:

The aims & objectives stated for this study which has been supportively elaborated and interpreted by the many findings and conclusions driven the various ways of this study. The conclusions were elaborated in the following ways.

In Shirgoan 67% people depend upon agriculture. In the process of general economic development, agriculture contributes 67%. It is therefore necessary and useful to acquaint it plays in the economic development. This will provide us a frame to discuss the present position for the development and progress.

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